

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ENDOLUMBAR OZONO-NOOTROPIC THERAPY IN THE PATIENTS WITH OUTCOMES OF TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY AND ARACHNOIDITIS

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Introduction: The outcomes of traumatic brain injury and arachnoiditis are the most casual case among the socially active segment of the population aged 18-40, which demonstrates the relevance of this problem. The ozone therapy is carried out by endolumbar method. The ozone will stimulate the immune system of the human body to fights against the viral and other pathological process in human organism, besides ozone has bactericidal properties.

ABSTRACT

The outcomes of traumatic brain injury and arachnoiditis are the most casual case among the socially active segment of the population aged 18-40, which demonstrates the relevance of this problem. The ozone therapy is carried out by endolumbar method. The ozone will stimulate the immune system of the human body to fights against the viral and other pathological process in human organism, besides ozone has bactericidal properties.

Aim: The aim of this research is to study the effectiveness of the ozone and nootropic endolumbar introduction for outcomes of traumatic brain injury and arachnoiditis of patients, who was hospitalized in the department of neurosurgeon for 3 last months.

Materials and methods: The data is being collected from 70 patients with (46 male and 24 female) with different outcomes with TBI from the age of 1-60 years from the neurosurgery department of

Samarkand state medical institute for January, February and March 2022 year.

All the patients were investigated by the exact same neuroimaging method and the lumbar puncture for the aspiration of the cerebrospinal fluid. The laboratory investigation of the CSF we conclude the level of the (Na, K, Fe, P, Cl, Mg) in the CSF by ROCHE -HITACHI analyzer after 1 months of treatment. Among the patient 28 (40%) patients were diagnosed with post-traumatic cerebral arachnoiditis in 29 (41%), 13 (18%) with post-traumatic epilepsy. For the endolumbar method the ozone is blown into the lumbar region by giving the local anesthesia by the method of the lumbar puncture the endolumbar dosage of injection is according to the age of the patients.

Result: In order to find out the effectiveness of the endolumbar after the treatment we study the composition of the CSF again to see the normalize level of the micro-macro elements presents in the CSF and bloodstream which is very necessary for the different activities of the brain. In the CSF investigation it has been shown the decreased level of Ca in 89.2% patients and the level of K, Cl is decreased in 100% of patients. The level of Na, P, Fe in the fluid

were normal but the averaged amount of Na, and P were high in 41% and 86.6% patients the level of Mg were also increased in 38.6 (32) patients.

After the endolumbar ozone-nootropic treatment the level of all the micro-macro elements were normalize. After the treatment the investigation of the CSF shows the normal level of the micro-macronutrients in the blood stream and CSF.

Conclusions: The imbalance in the level of the micro-macro elements in the CSF can lead to different metabolic disorders and can lead to several neurological changes so the introduction of ozone and nootropic treatment in the endolumbar can normalize the level of the micro-macronutrients in the blood stream and CSF and can improve the conditions of the patients and restoration of the clinical neurological disorders. the positive result with our patients who we have performed the l and endolumbar ozone nootropic treatment for the TBI and Arachnoiditis. The data provided by us testify to the high efficiency using of the ozone combined with nootropics in various diseases and gives a favourably result in the nearest period of treatment.

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